

O'YINLAR NAZARIYASIDA MATRITSANING RO'LI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada turli xildagi ikkita o'yinchidan iborat o'yinlarni yechishda matritsa tuzish yo'li bilan matritsaning o'yinlar nazariyasiga tatbiqi va aniq misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'chish, satr, ustun, matritsa, musbat, manfiy, strategiya, maksimum, minimum, optimal strategiya, egar nuqta, pozitsiya.

Ikkita o'yinchidan iborat o'yinni qaraylik. Odatiy tarzda A o'yinchini mumkin bo'lgan $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ ko'chishlarga ega satr o'yinchisi, B o'yinchini esa $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ mumkin bo'lgan ustun ko'chishlar o'yinchisi sifatida belgilaylik. Har bir ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) va ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) lar uchun a_{ij} orqali agar A o'yinchi i satr bo'yicha va B o'yinchi j ustun bo'yicha ko'chganda B o'yinchining A o'yinchini tutib olishidagi o'yin tugashini belgilaymiz. Bu sonlar o'yin tugashi matritsasini hosil qiladi:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Matritsa elementlari musbat, manfiy yoki nol bo'lishi mumkin. Faraz qilaylik, har bir $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ lar uchun A o'yinchi i satrga p_i ehtimol bilan va har bir $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ lar uchun B o'yinchi j satrga q_j ehtimol bilan ko'chsin. U holda ravshanki,

$$p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_m = 1 \text{ va } q_1 + q_2 + \dots + q_n = 1$$

bo'ladi. O'yinchilar bir-biriga bog'liqsiz ko'chishlar hosil qiladi deb qabul qilamiz. U holda har bir $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ va $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ lar uchun $p_i q_j$ son A o'yinchi i satr bo'yicha va B o'yinchi j ustun bo'yicha ko'chish ehtimolligini beradi. U holda quyidagi qo'sh yig'indi kutilgan B o'yinchi A o'yinchini tutishidagi o'yin tugashini ifodalaydi:

$$E_C(p, q) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} p_i q_j.$$

Quyidagi

$$p = (p_1 \ p_2 \ \dots \ p_m) \text{ va } q = \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ \vdots \\ q_n \end{pmatrix}$$

matritsalar mos ravishda A va B o'yinchilar strategiyalarini ifodalaydi. Ravshanki, kutilgan o'yin tugashi

$$E_C(p, q) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} p_i q_j = (p_1 \ p_2 \ \dots \ p_m) \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & \dots & a_{nm} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ \vdots \\ q_m \end{pmatrix} = pCq.$$

Endi biz quyidagi masalalarni qaraymiz: Faraz qilaylik C matritsa fiksirlangan bo'lsin. A o'yinchi kutilgan $E_C(p, q)$ o'yin tugashini maksimumga erishtiradigan p strategiyani tanlashi mumkinmi? Shu o'rinda B o'yinchi kutilgan $E_C(p, q)$ o'yin tugashini minimumga erishtiradigan q strategiyani tanlashi mumkinmi?

Teorema (O'yin tugashining fundamental teoremasi). A o'yinchining har qanday p strategiyasi va B o'yinchining har qanday q strategiyasi uchun shunday p^* va q^* strategiyalar mavjudki,

$$E_C(p^*, q) \geq E_C(p^*, q^*) \geq E_C(p, q^*)$$

bo'ladi.

Eslatma. p^* strategiya A o'yinchining optimal strategiyasi sifatida va q^* strategiya B o'yinchining optimal strategiyasi sifatida ma'lum. $E_C(p^*, q^*)$ miqdor o'yinning qiymati hisoblanadi. Optimal strategiyalar yagona bo'lishi zarur emas. Agar p^{**} va q^{**} lar boshqa optimal strategiyalar bo'lsa, u holda

$$E_C(p^*, q^*) = E_C(p^{**}, q^{**})$$

bo'ladi.

Bu yerda o'yin tugashi matritsasi C egar nuqtalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Agar a_{ij} element C matritsaning satrlaridagi eng kichik va ustunlaridagi eng katta element bo'lsa, u egar nuqta deyiladi. Bu holda strategiyalar quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$p^* = (0 \ \dots \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0) \text{ va } q = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Bu yerda 1 lar i pozitsiyada p^* va j pozitsiyada q^* optimal strategiyalarning sodir bo'lishlaridir, shuning uchun o'yinning qiymati a_{ij} bo'ladi.

Misol. Sportchilar maktabi o'qituvchisi eshkakchilar (A) va kriketchilar (B) orasidan 100 ta talaba tanlashni talab qildi. Talabalar o'zlaricha tarkib tuzolmaydilar va eshkakchilar murabbiysi hamda kriketchilar murabbiysi tanlaydi.

Maktab 3 ta

eshkakchilar murabbiysi hamda 4 ta kriketchilar murabbiylarini yollashi mumkin. Har bir senariyda eshkakchilar kriketchilardan oldin tanlanishi quyidagicha, bu yerda A_1, A_2 va A_3 lar mumkin bo'lgan eshkakchilar murabbiylari va B_1, B_2, B_3 va B_4 lar kriketchilar murabbiylari belgilangan:

	B_1	B_1	B_1	B_1
A_1	75	50	45	60
A_1	20	60	30	55
A_1	45	70	35	30

Misol uchun, agar A_2 va B_1 murabbiylar tanlangan bo'lsa, u holda 20 ta talaba eshkakchilardan va qolgan 80 ta talaba kriketchilardan tanlangan bo'ladi.

Dastlab biz har bir elementdan 50 ni ayiramiz va o'yin tugashi matritsasini hosil qilamiz:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 25 & 0 & -5 & 10 \\ -30 & 10 & -20 & 5 \\ -5 & 20 & -15 & -20 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Misol uchun, yuqori chap element agar har bir sport 50 ta talaba bilan boshlansa, u holda 25 ta kriketchi talabalar eshkakchilarga yutqazadilr. Birinchi satr va uchinchi ustunda joylashgan -5 soni egar nuqta bo'ladi, shuning uchun eshkakchilar uchun optimal strategiya A_1 murabbiydan foydalanish hamda kriketchilar uchun optimal strategiya B_3 murabbiydan foydalanishdir.

Umuman, egar nuqtalar mavjud bo'lmasligi mumkin, shuning uchun masala

qat'iy aniqlanmagan. U holda optimal masalaning yechimi chiziqli dasturlashtirish usullar yordamida topiladi. Quyidagi o'yin tugashi matritsasi 2×2

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

matritsa bo'lsa va egar nuqtalarni o'z ichiga olmasa, u holda biz $p_2 = 1 - p_1$ va $q_2 = 1 - q_1$ deb yozishimiz mumkin. U holda

$$E_C(p, q) = a_{11}p_1q_1 + a_{12}p_1(1 - q_1) + a_{21}q_1(1 - p_1) + a_{22}(1 - p_1)(1 - q_1) = \\ = ((a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22})p_1 - (a_{22} - a_{21})q_1) + (a_{12} - a_{22})p_1 + a_{22}.$$

Faraz qilaylik

$$p_1 = p_1^* = \frac{a_{22} - a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}}$$

bo'lsin. U holda q ga bog'liqsiz holda

$$E_C(p^*, q) = \frac{(a_{12} - a_{22})(a_{22} - a_{21})}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}} + a_{22} = \frac{a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}}$$

bo'ladi. Xuddi shunday agar

$$q_1 = q_1^* = \frac{a_{22} - a_{12}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}}$$

bo'lsa, u holda p ga bog'liqsiz holda

$$E_C(p, q^*) = \frac{a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}}$$

bo'ladi. Demak, barcha p va q strategiyalar uchun

$$E_C(p^*, q) = E_C(p^*, q^*) = E_C(p, q^*)$$

bo'ladi.

Ta'kidlash kerakki,

$$p^* = \left(\frac{a_{22} - a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}} \quad \frac{a_{11} - a_{12}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}} \right), \quad (1)$$

$$q^* = \left(\frac{a_{22} - a_{12}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}} \quad \frac{a_{11} - a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}} \right). \quad (2)$$

Bundan,

$$E_C(p^*, q^*) = \frac{a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}}{a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{21} + a_{22}}.$$

tenglik hosil bo'ladi.

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